

Metal Chelates Of Xylenol Orange with Vanadium (V) and Niobium (V). A Spectrophotometric Study.

Badri Vishal Agarwala and Arun K. Dey

The composition and stability of vanadium-DCAC and niobium-DCAC chelates have been studied by spectrophotometric measurements. The red coloured chelates ($\lambda_{\max}$ 490 m μ at pH 5.0 and 590 m μ at pH 5.5 respectively) have a composition 1:1 (metal:ligand) in each case. The chelates are stable between pH 3.5 to 6.5 (V-DCAC) and 2.0 to 7.0 (Nb-DCAC). The average values of $\log K$ as calculated by three methods are 4.5 and 4.3 at 25° (pH 5.0 and 5.5) respectively.

In earlier communications from these laboratories the metal chelates of xylenol orange (3,3'-bis-[N,N-di(carboxymethyl)-aminomethyl]-o-cresolsulphonphthalein; abbr. DCAC) with gallium, indium and thallium¹ and the rare earths² have been described. In the present communication, the metal chelates of vanadium (V) and niobium (V) have been described. Tantalum does not form a complex with this ligand. Considerable amount of work has been done on niobium-DCAC complex³⁻⁵, but the results are conflicting. The spectrophotometric determination of vanadium (IV) with DCAC has been described by Otomo⁶.

It was considered to be of interest to carry out detailed studies on the DCAC chelates of vanadium and niobium and the results are reported here.

EXPERIMENTAL

A standard solution of vanadium was prepared by dissolving ammonium vanadate (AnalaR, B.D.H.) in hot water. A standard solution of niobium was prepared by fusing niobium pentoxide (Johnson, Matthey & Co.) with potassium hydrogen sulphate and then extracting the melt in hot tartaric acid solution. It was standardised by the cupferron method. Other chemicals employed were of reagent grade. Standard solution of DCAC was prepared in 10% aqueous ethanol.

The apparatus and method were as reported earlier¹.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nature of the complexes formed: Mixtures containing varying proportion of metal solution: DCAC were prepared and the absorbance in each case was measured at suitable

1. C. D. Dwivedi, K. N. Munshi and A. K. Dey, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 301.
2. K. N. Munshi and A. K. Dey, *Chemist-Analyst*, 1964, 53, 105.
3. K. L. Chang and B. L. Goydith, *Talanta*, 1962, 9, 987.
4. S. V. Elinson and L. I. Pobedina, *Zhur. Analit. Khim.*, 1963, 18, 734.
5. A. K. Babko and M. I. Shtokalo, *Zhur. Analit. Khim.*, 1962, 17, 1058; *Dopovidí Akad. Nauk. Ukrain R.S.R.*, 1961, 9, 1179.
6. M. Otomo, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1964, 37, 504.

intervals between a range of wavelength from 400 $m\mu$ to 600 $m\mu$. The maximum absorbance lies at 490 $m\mu$ for vanadium-DCAC chelate (pH 5.0, Fig. 1) and 530 $m\mu$ in case of niobium-DCAC chelate (pH 5.5, Fig. 2) whereas the λ_{max} of DCAC alone was 440 $m\mu$ at these pH values. The formation of only one complex under the present conditions of study is indicated in each case.

FIG. 1. Absorption spectra of mixtures of vanadium and DCAC.

Curve A : reagent $8.0 \times 10^{-5}M$
 Curve B : $c = 16.0 \times 10^{-5}M$ ($p = 0.5$)
 Curve C : $c = 8.0 \times 10^{-5}M$ ($p = 1$)
 Curve D : $c = 4.0 \times 10^{-5}M$ ($p = 2$)
 Curve E : $c = 2.67 \times 10^{-5}M$ ($p = 3$)
 $p = c'/c = \text{Concn. of DCAC/metal ion.}$

FIG. 2. Absorption spectra of mixtures of niobium and DCAC. Concentration: the same as in Fig. 1.

Stoichiometry of the components: The composition of the chelate was established by two methods viz., (i) the method of continuous variations (Figs. 3-4) and (ii) the mole ratio

FIG. 3. Determination of the composition from method of continuous variations, equimolecular solutions-V-DCAC system: Curve A, $c = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}M$, Curve B, $c = 1.33 \times 10^{-4}M$, Curve C, $c = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$.

FIG. 4. Determination of the composition from method of continuous variations, equimolecular solutions-Nb-DCAC system. Concentrations: the same as in Fig. 3.

method and is 1 : 1. Observations were made at several wavelengths and the composition in each case was 1 : 1.

Ionic strength could not be maintained due to the colour fading with electrolytes.

Evaluation of the stability constant: Three methods were employed for the determination of apparent stability constant⁷⁻⁹. (i) Method of Dey and associates (a), (ii) Job's method of continuous variations using non-equimolecular solutions (b) and (iii) Mole ratio method (c).

Stability constant by method (a): Concentrations of metal ions (a) and ligand (b) in the various curves for an absorbance of 0.12 (vanadium complex) and 0.07-niobium complex concentration same for both complexes—were read from the curves. The concentration of complex x was calculated and thereby the value of $K^?$.

TABLE I

Stability constants by method (b)

Concentrations and the volume of the metal ions at the peak using non-equimolecular solutions

System	Total volume 25 ml		
	$c \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$\left(\frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2}\right)$ ($=c/c$)	Volume of the metal ion at the peak (ml)
V (V)—DCAC	1.00	2.0	15.0
	2.00	0.5	10.0
Nb (V)—DCAC	1.00	2.0	15.0
	2.00	0.5	10.0

TABLE II

Stability constants by method (c)

Values of concentrations, E_m , E_s and α (degree of dissociation)

System	$c \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	E_m	E_s	α
V (V)—DCAC	1.00	1.000	0.700	0.30
	0.80	0.870	0.590	0.32
Nb (V)—DCAC	1.00	0.800	0.600	0.25
	0.80	0.500	0.370	0.26

The values of the constants are in Table III

TABLE III

Stability constants of the chelates at 25°

System	pH	log K	Method
V (V)—DCAC	5.0	4.0 ± 0.1	(a)
		4.7 ± 0.1	(b)
		4.8 ± 0.1	(c)
Nb (V)—DCAC	5.5	4.9 ± 0.2	(a)
		4.7 ± 0.1	(b)
		5.0 ± 0.0	(c)

The authors thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for financing the work and for the award of a fellowship to one of them (B.V.A.)

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD,
ALLAHABAD.

Received, August 29, 1966

1. A. K. Mukherji and A. K. Dey, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314; *Analyt. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 18, 324.
2. P. Job, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928; *Ann. Chim.*, 1926, 9, 113.
3. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Analyt. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.